

An Engineering Assessment of the Static Residual Strength of Composite Laminates With Impact-Induced Damages: Integrated Procedure Based on 3D FEM and 2D Theoretical Analyses and Experimental Investigations

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ABSTRACT

A new approach based on combined FEM-based Global-Local numerical analysis, semiempirical modelling and experimental investigations is proposed for assessing the static uniaxial residual strength of impact damaged composites. The approach is founded on an *Energetic Equivalence Criterion* for reducing impact-induced damages to equivalent holes. The analysis and assessment procedure is based on: (1) NDE geometrical characterisation of damaged material volumes providing accurate characterisation of both in-plane damage extensions and through-thickness distributions, (2) reduction of the actual damaged material volumes to *equivalent inclusions* with reduced mechanical properties, (3) reduction of inclusions to *equivalent holes*, (4) testing of *notched composite laminates* for the calibration of a tailored semiempirical model providing a direct and simple correlation between the residual strength and the damage size.

INTRODUCTION

The prediction of residual strengths of impact damaged composite structural elements is essential for substantiating the criticality of induced damages and for assessing in-service safety margin and residual life of load bearing composite structures. In order to design damage tolerant composite structures, several methods and approaches have been proposed for evaluating the behaviour and for predicting the residual strength of damaged composite laminates. The finite element method, is very powerful but requires comprehensive knowledge on the occurring damage and fracture mechanisms and effective expertise on accurate modelling and computational techniques [1-3]. FEM-based analysis tools are capable of providing reliable evaluations and predictions, irrespective of material systems and loading conditions but if damage propagations have to be simulated up to ultimate failure, they can be very time consuming and expensive. The assessment of the static uniaxial residual strength of both notched and impact damaged composite laminates is relevant to maintenance and health monitoring of structural systems and for practical engineering problems, simple and reliable predictive methods/tools are required. For this reason, semiempirical modelling techniques have been devised and proposed [4-5] but their efficacy and reliability is always doubtful because they do not take the elementary damage and fracture mechanisms into account. Semiempirical models, are very simple and inexpensive but they always need a tailored calibration as soon as either the material system or the loading condition change. In dealing with post-impact compressive strengths, it is of course possible to calibrate the semiempirical models by a direct best fitting of experimental data, but the reliability of the material/load dependent parameters is

undetermined because of the uncertainty of post-impact experimental data. In fact, experimental evidences show that impact events with the same energy on alike specimens do not always occur with the same effects, in terms of damage patterns and sizes, and residual strengths carried out from tests on impacted specimens are generally affected by significant scattering particularly for compressive loading. Moreover, damage and failure mechanisms in fiber composite laminates must be properly interpreted as far as scale-up effects are concerned and appropriate extrapolation methods have to be devised for employing results of strength tests on small-scale specimens to actual structural components. Conversely, residual strengths of composite panels containing "standard notches", e.g. holes, are much more reliable because they are generally characterised by narrow scattering and low standard deviations and scale-up effects also can be managed in a better way. From the above concepts a new analysis procedure has been defined with the aim to develop an analysis tool capable of addressing the following issues: (a) material dependent effects, (b) load dependent factors and (c) geometry and scale-up effects. The primary thrust of the proposed method is to provide an efficient computational tool for sound and reliable static residual strength predictions, taking damage/failure mechanisms and scale-up effects into account.

PHYSICAL MODELLING OF IMPACT-INDUCED DAMAGES IN COMPOSITES

Depending on the impact energies, stacking sequences and material systems damages in composite laminates take place with different patterns. For low velocity impacts intraply matrix cracking and delaminations are the two major damages. Delaminations, are of particular concern because under compressive loading they may buckle and propagate in unstable manner. Damage patterns for the specific composite laminates tested in the present study are schematically shown in Fig.1. It was observed that for low energy impacts, delaminations take place at the most critical interface and spreads through the thickness with a cone-like pattern up to the back ply. With high energy impacts, delaminations take place with the same cone-like pattern, from the impact side to the back one, but an extended delamination take place at the back ply of the laminate. From fracture behaviour of laminates with impact-induced damages or holes and from continuum mechanics concepts, it is inferred that residual strengths of damaged laminates is higher then residual strengths of laminates containing holes of sizes equal to the mean damage sizes. In fact, the damaged material volume can be assumed as a layered elastic inclusion with perfectly bonded plies, with reduced stiffness but still having a load carrying capacity.

Fig 1 - Damage patterns induced by low and high energy impacts in composite laminates

The analysis of stress-strain fields in a laminate containing a hole or an inclusion of equal size and with reduced elastic properties, reveals that both the stress concentration factor and the strain energy for the notched laminate are higher than those of the laminate containing the inclusion; it is

then reasonable to consider an inclusion as a hole having a smaller size. In order to define an *equivalence criterion*, the main issue to be addressed is the choice of the physical parameter on the basis of which the equivalence is established. In the proposed approach, the Strain Energy (SE) has been chosen as the most consistent and relevant physical parameter. Admitting that damage and fracture processes take place in the *process zone (PZ)*, which is within an *intense energy area (IEA)* surrounding the damaged area (see Fig.2), it is inferred that damage and fracture processes make use of the strain energy gathered in the IEA, which behaves as a reservoir of energy.

Fig.2 - Damage and fracture model

ENGINEERING ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT DAMAGED COMPOSITES LAMINATES: BASIC PHILOSOPHY

The objective of the study was to define and validate an analysis procedure and a related computational tool for assessing the static residual strength of impact damaged composite laminates. The following requirements were established for the procedure/tool: (a) it must be simple and reliable, (b) it must provide predictions with a high confidence, (c) it must be capable of accounting for damage and fracture mechanisms and (d) it must be capable of handling geometry and scale-up effects. For accomplishing these requirements, it was decided to combine a FEM-based Global-Local analysis procedure and a semiempirical models calibrated via tailored experimental tests. By the FEM-GL analysis the damage and fracture mechanisms as well as scale-up effects can be properly modelled and analysed and hence the material and/or load dependent factors can be taken into account. On the other hand, the semiempirical model provide a very simple and direct relationship between the static residual strength and damage sizes. The overall analysis procedure for the residual strength assessment is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3 - Analysis procedure for assessing the static Residual Compressive Strength (RCS)

For developing the GL analysis, a tailored computational model was implemented for identifying the IEA around the impact-induced damages and holes. The IEA is determined by the boundary of

the stress riser at hand, i.e. the damaged material volume or the hole, and the boundary defined by points in which the maximum in-plane stress components assume a value differing by a small percentage difference from the corresponding applied far-field stress.

WORK OF FRACTURE AND DAMAGE-HOLE EQUIVALENCE CRITERION

Overall failures are consequence of the initiation and propagation mechanisms of elementary damages and fractures occurring at micro- meso- and macro-scales. Damages and fractures are dissipative processes which can be analysed by Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) and Fracture Mechanics (FM). The overall work of fracture can be evaluated by summing up the energy dissipated in each fracture mechanism occurring under compressive loading:

$$W_f = w_{mb} + w_{sc} + w_{db} \quad (1)$$

where w_{mb} , w_{sc} and w_{db} are the work of microbuckling, shear crippling and delamination buckling respectively. The statement of the proposed Energetic Equivalence Criterion (EEC) is: *an impact-induced damage is equivalent to a hole if both of them require the same work of fracture up to the ultimate failure. Because the work of fracture is extracted from the Potential Energy of Deformation (PED) stored within their respective intense energy area, IEA, a damage is equivalent to a hole if their individual PED, gathered within the IEA, are equal.* This statement is applicable only if the failure and damage mechanisms are the same for the impact-induced damage and the hole. The lay-up of the laminate considered in this study was $[0/45/90/-45/0_{1/2}]_{2S}$. By FEM-based Global-Local analyses of the elastic stress fields, [6], it was verified that under compressive loading for such a laminate the interlaminar stresses are not critical and if the impact-induced delaminations are properly constrained for excluding delamination buckling, the prevailing elementary failure mechanisms are fiber microbuckling and shear crippling. Of course, in actual delaminated composite panels acted upon by compressive loading, delamination buckling is one of the major fracture mechanisms. In the present study only microbuckling and shear crippling were considered and it was assumed that they are the only two fracture mechanisms occurring in laminates containing either impact-induced damages or holes. The proposed EEC can be applied by evaluating either the different elementary works of fracture, by using appropriate micromechanical models, or by evaluating the global PED related to each stress riser. The first way is more accurate but even more expensive and time-consuming. At present, the PED has been evaluated for estimating the diameter of the "equivalent holes". The plies of the laminates were assumed to have three planes of symmetry and by defining the strain energy density function for the orthotropic material, the PED accumulated within the intense energy volume is easily found by integration with respect to the volume:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} \epsilon_{ij} \quad \text{PED} = \iiint_{\omega} S(x_1, x_2, x_3) d\omega \quad (2)$$

It must be remarked that within the IEA surrounding the damaged material or the hole the stress fields are affected by local steep gradients (in-plane stress components) and even singularities (through-thickness stress components). Therefore, the contribution of these stress components to the PED is significant and the FEM-GL analysis must be developed by suitable models in order to carry out accurate estimations. However, for computing the radius of the equivalent holes the differences of the PEDs, related to damaged material volumes and holes respectively, are minimised and hence if the computational errors affecting the two PEDs are the same, errors affecting the radius estimation are also minimised due to cancellation effects. For evaluating the radius of the equivalent holes, an optimisation procedure was developed in which the objective function was the difference of PEDs, the design variable was the radius of the hole and appropriate constraints have been defined in terms of minimum and maximum hole radius values.

2D ANALYTICAL/3D FEM-BASED GLOBAL-LOCAL ANALYSIS, SEMIEMPIRICAL MODELLING AND APPLICATION EXAMPLE

FEM analyses provide useful insights into the stress-strain and energy fields and by appropriate "zooming" techniques very detailed computations can be performed. Because of singularities and steep gradients affecting the local stress fields, a FEM-based GL procedure (see refs. [7,8]) was applied. The global analyses have been carried out by using analytical solutions of anisotropic plates containing elastic inclusions or holes (see ref. [9], pp. 171-217). The reduced elastic properties of inclusions have been estimated by applying the model proposed by K. O'Brien, [10], which is based on the classical laminate theory. From global analyses the boundaries of IEAs and the related displacement boundary conditions have been evaluated. The local analyses have been carried out by defining suitable 3D finite element models where displacement boundary conditions, representing the actions of the "outer region" on the "inner region", have been enforced. In modelling impact damaged laminates, i.e. containing delaminations, kinematics contact elements have been used but contact friction between sublaminates was not considered. Fig. 4 shows the in-plane stress distributions and the IEAs evaluated for an impact-induced damage modelled as a single delamination. Because of some uncertainties affecting the available US-NDE characterisation of the delamination through-thickness position, different configurations have been considered and it was noticed a significant sensitivity of the IEA extension.

Fig. 4 - 2D analytical stress solutions and IEA mappings

section of the laminate, if the laminate is oriented with the major axis at 90° with respect to the loading direction, the undamaged resistant section is lower and also the overall residual strength could be lower.

It was also observed that the ratio between the maximum and minimum delamination sizes as well as the orientation of the delamination with respect to the principal laminate axes influence the extent of IEAs. A parametric study was carried out in order to be confident on the sensitivities of the IEA, whose estimation strongly influence the evaluation of PEDs and hence the computation of the equivalent hole radius. Both the through-thickness position and the orientation of delaminations have been changed; the variations of the normalized IEA are shown in Fig.5. It is observed that the orientation of the delamination is a relevant factor. In particular, it can be stated that if the delamination has the major axis oriented along the loading direction, then the local radius of curvature at points located at 90° with respect to the loading direction is higher and then the gradient of the in-plane stress components is less steep but more spreaded with a larger IEA. However, it must be remarked that by considering the net resistant

Fig. 5 - Parametric analysis on geometrical factors affecting the IEA extensions

Fig. 6 - Effects of the delamination depth on engineering constants of the elastic inclusion

From Figs.5(a) and 6 it is observed that the delamination through-thickness position influence in the same way both the stiffness reduction of the damaged material and the IEA. This is justified because the ratio between the elastic properties of the damaged material volume, assumed as an inclusion, and those of the undamaged material affect both the stress concentration factor and the in-plane stress distributions. Because the extension and shape of the IEA is defined on the basis of the in-plane stress distributions, there is a direct correlation between the material properties degradation and the IEA. There is another important effect, related to the delamination through-thickness position, to be considered in the local FEM 3D modelling. Depending on the interface at which the delamination is initiated, the sublaminates may have a coupled membrane-flexural behaviour giving rise to warping effects. Such warping effects must

be carefully taken into account because they can give rise to contact phenomena between the sublaminates and they can also be critical as far as the local delamination buckling is concerned. In the present study, this problem has been considered to some extent by using contact elements without friction. Fig. 7 shows the 3D FEM model of a totally delaminated laminate, containing four delaminations. Without using contact elements compenetration phenomena take place, losing the physics of the phenomenon; however even with kinematics contact elements warping phenomena occurs. Fig. 8.a shows the out-of-plane displacement obtained by a 3D finite element model of a delaminated specimen with antibuckling constraints. The deformed section view has been magnified

in order to visualise the bulging of the delaminated portion of the specimen within two antibuckling stiffeners is evident.

Fig.7- 3D FEM analysis of a delaminated laminate

Fig.8 - 3D FEM model of a delaminated specimen with out-of-plane constraints (antibuckling frame)

Fig.9 - Correlation of numerical RCS estimations with the calibrated semiempirical power-type model

The semiempirical model used in this study is based on LEFM concepts, [11], and it was formulated following the approach proposed by Waddupons et. al, [12]. Assuming a crack-like defect within the composite laminate and by applying the LEFM theory, failure occurs when:

$$K_{IC} = \sigma_c (\pi C)^m \quad (3)$$

where: σ_c is the residual strength, $2C$ is the crack length and m is a material dependent constant. Assuming that the final failure of an unnotched laminate is due to an intrinsic defect of size $2C_0$, the behaviour of an unnotched laminate can also be analysed in terms of fracture mechanics:

$$K_{IC} = \sigma_0 (\pi C_0)^m \quad (4)$$

where σ_0 is the typical strength of the material. From Eqns (3) and (4) the following relationship is obtained:

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_0} = \left(\frac{C_0}{C}\right)^m \quad (5)$$

representing a power-type model with two unknown material dependent parameters, C_0 and m . Fig. 9 shows the correlation of numerical Residual Compressive Strengths, RCS, estimated via the equivalent hole concept and the semiempirical model, calibrated by the RCS experimental data obtained by testing laminates containing holes. It is observed that the proposed analysis and assessment approach is always conservative and provide accurate RCS prediction. It require, in any case, a very detailed and reliable NDE characterisation of the impact-induced damages.

CONCLUSIONS

A combined analytical, numerical and experimental analysis procedure for assessing the static residual strength of composite laminates containing impact-induced damages was developed. The proposed analysis procedure allows to carry out very accurate and highly confident calibration of semiempirical model for post-impact residual strength predictions by using residual strength data carried out by testing laminate containing equivalent holes. The combination of FEM based analysis and semiempirical modelling allows to take damage and failure mechanisms into account providing an analysis tool with an underlying physical basis. The proposed analysis procedure has been validated only for a specific laminate configuration and material system under compressive loading. Residual strengths obtained via equivalent hole concept have been correlated with a semiempirical model calibrated using residual strength data of alike laminate containing holes and it was found a good correlation. The proposed modelling and analysis procedure can be improved by taking the progressive nature of failure into account and by modelling both the delamination buckling and contact phenomena.

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